

3-D-Printed Bandpass Filter Using Conical Posts Interlaced Vertically

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Abstract— A new class of filters using conical post resonators is presented. The proposed structure consists of stacked rectangular cavities where each cavity has a capacitive conical resonating post positioned in its center. The resonator is very similar to that used in combline filters, but in this case, taking advantage of the stacked arrangement and of the conical shape, each post has its upper part partially inserted in the hollow base of the post above it. The resulting structure is more compact than the classical combline filter, whereas the Q-factor is very similar. In order to validate the proposed structure, a doublet filter prototype has been designed, manufactured using additive manufacturing techniques and tested.

Keywords— Additive manufacturing, 3-D printing, bandpass filter, conical resonator, combline filter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Comblines filters are often used (e.g., in radio base stations) because of their smaller size compared to waveguide filters, their relatively good quality factor, and their wide spurious free range. Several implementations have been successfully proposed in recent years, some exploiting new geometries that allow to the reduction of the capacitive loading for a given length of the resonator [1], or to improve power handling capability [2]. In [3], a dual bandpass filter is implemented by two stacked rows of cavities with cylindrical posts. Each cavity row generates one of the bands of the dual-band filter. The idea is to save volume by exploiting the hollow internal part of the post in the upper cavity for housing part of the post in the lower cavity. As a consequence, the post in the upper cavity shall have a radius larger than that of the lower cavity. This is acceptable when the two cavities are tuned for different bands as in the proposed dual-band application, but it could be a problem in case of a single band. Beside the filter geometry, novel manufacturing techniques may help in obtaining high performance filters. In this regard, additive manufacturing (AM), commonly known as 3-D printing, has attracted a growing interest due to its great potential in fast prototyping and flexibility.

AM technology allows for the manufacturing of complex geometric structures. Light structures can be obtained when AM technologies based on plastic material are used. As a result, AM has become an interesting solution for engineers to fabricate microwave components [4], as for example antennas [5], couplers [6], and filters [7]. In [8], the high flexibility of the AM technology has been exploited to obtain posts with

Fig. 1. Conical resonator.

non-conventional shape and interconnections that allow for inline compact filters with transmission zeros.

In this paper, a new class of filters with conical posts that exploit the high flexibility of the 3-D printing technology is presented. Similarly to [3], the hollow part of the post is used for housing the post situated below, but on the contrary of the structure in [3], thanks to the conical shape, posts in staked cavities can be identical and can resonate at the same frequency. This results in a filter with Q-factor similar to that of the classical combline filter but with reduced dimensions.

II. CONICAL RESONATOR

Conical and cylindrical resonant posts behave in a very similar way. In both cases, the field is more intense around the top of the post, where the capacitive effect is created by the proximity between post top and cavity ceiling. In Fig. 2, the field distribution for the resonator with conical post is shown. As can be seen, the cavity height is lower than the conical post height and the cover of the cavity has a conical bump allowing the housing of the post. As illustrated later on, this bump can be used as the conical post of an additional cavity positioned at the top of the first cavity. On the other hand, as previously stated, the unloaded Q-factor (Q_u) of the structure in Fig. 1 is similar to that of the classical cylindrical post resonator. As an example, for the resonator reported in [2], the nominal value of the Q_u is 3591 at 2.5 GHz. With the proposed conical structure, the same Q_u at the same frequency is obtained with a reduction of about 30% of the volume.

III. DOUBLET IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed resonator can be exploited for the design of any order filter. To demonstrate the suitability of the proposed structure, in this paper a second-order filter is considered.

Fig. 2. Conical resonator: electric field.

Fig. 3. Second-order filter: a) Lateral size view; b) Dimetric view; c) Topology.

A complete view of the proposed structure can be seen in Fig. 3. It consists of two resonators placed on top of each other, with two apertures located sideways and coaxial feeding probes representing input and output. As shown in the previous section, the resonators have conical shapes with two different radii in the upper and lower part. Such a structure realizes the inline doublet of Fig. 3(c). In particular, the position of the coaxial feeding probes controls the input and output coupling coefficients k_{S1} and k_{2L} . The size of the apertures between the two cavities controls the coupling k_{12} between the two resonators. Finally, the height of the conical posts can be used for a fine control of the resonance frequency as shown in Fig. 4.

In Fig. 5, the external Q-factor Q_e as a function of the position $f_{p1}(f_{p2})$ of the input (output) feeding coaxial is shown. As expected, and analogously to the cylindrical post, the higher the position, the lower the Q_e . On the other hand, Fig. 6 represents the value of the coupling k_{12} as a function of the aperture size l_{iris} . Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 can be used to obtain the physical dimensions of the filter design. Therefore, for the purpose of this paper, a Chebyshev response has been considered, with frequency centered at 1.75 GHz, and fractional bandwidth of 5%. According to Fig. 3(c), this corresponds to the following values of the coupling $k_{S1} = 0.266$ and $k_{12} = 0.0765$. The initial value for the height

Fig. 4. Resonance frequency versus h_{cone} .

Fig. 5. External Q-factor versus the physical parameter f_{p1} of the input.

Fig. 6. Values for the f_1 and f_2 (representing the odd and even frequency of the doublet) and the corresponding k values versus the physical distance l_{iris} .

can be estimated using the graph from Fig. 4, which gives a value of 35.65 mm at 1.75 GHz. The external quality factor Q_e can be easily evaluated from k_{S1} :

$$Q_e = \frac{1}{k_{S1}^2} = 14.13. \quad (1)$$

From Fig. 5, this leads to a value of $f_{p1} = f_{p2} = 14.75$ mm. As Fig. 6 indicates, $k_{12} = 0.0765$ can be realized by an aperture length $l_{iris} = 32$ mm. Such values have been used as a starting point. The final response have been obtained after an optimization process. In Table. 1 the dimensions of the final structure are listed.

IV. 3-D-PRINTED FILTER PROTOTYPING

In order to study the feasibility of the proposed filter, the manufacturing of the prototype has been carried out

Table 1. Filter dimensions.

Symbols	Name	mm
h_{cone}	Resonator Height	36.18
h_i	Internal Height	12.95
d_u	Upper Diameter	9.2
d_l	Lower Diameter	32.2
h_{cavity}	Cavity Height	20.7
t_{iris}	Iris Thickness	6.9
l_{iris}	Iris Length	33.1
f_{p1}	Feeding Probe - Input	14.5
f_{p2}	Feeding Probe - Output	14
w_{cavity}	Cavity Size	46
t_{wall}	Wall Thickness	2.5
d_c	Conductor Diameter	3
l_{s1}	Screw Insertion 1	10.7
l_{s2}	Screw Insertion 2	10

using PolyJet printing technology, followed by a metallization process of copper using electroplating. The photograph of the manufactured prototype is shown in Fig. 7. Fig. 8 shows a full-wave simulation of the structure designed in the previous section. The results depict an insertion loss of 1.3 dB and a minimum return loss of 16.4 dB through the passband. In comparison with the simulation, the response is shifted 30 MHz. The discrepancies between both insertion losses are attributed to the metallization of the internal conductor, specifically due to the small thickness of layer applied to the fabricated prototype and the difficulty to apply this conductivity layer of copper evenly around the structure. Moreover, the filter includes screws inserted horizontally for a more precise tuning of the frequency. The Q_u of the simulated structure from Fig. 3 is 1400 (computed for aluminum with conductivity $\sigma = 38$ MS/m), whereas the simulated Q_u using eigenmode solver from ANSYS High-Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS) for a single resonator is 3900 (computed for aluminum with conductivity $\sigma = 38$ MS/m) at the same frequency.

V. CONCLUSION

A new type of filter based on conical resonators has been reported. A two-pole filter has been designed, manufactured using 3-D printing techniques, and metallized by using electroplating. The proposed structure allows for the reduction of the volume, while maintaining a Q_u similar to that of the classical coaxial resonators using cylindrical posts. The results of the manufactured prototype show a similar response as the simulation, proving the viability of creating this type of filters using AM techniques.

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Fig. 7. Manufactured filter: a) Disassembled structure before the metallization; b) Assembled structure before the metallization; c) Bottom part of the metallized structure; d) Bottom part of the metallized structure with connector SMA.

Fig. 8. Simulated and measured response (S-parameters) of the filter prototype.

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